

OVERVIEW OF MACRO SCALE MODEL FOR LARGE SCALE RIVER BASIN

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Abstract:

Water resources management needs a proper way to handle a particular approach. It involves various hydrological components. There is impact on various environmental parameter like land use and land cover, agriculture, water usage due to human encroachment on environment at significant level. The impact leads to periodic hydrologic change. It thus becomes necessary to understand and quantify various hydrological components of the catchment for efficient management of water. Runoff representing the response of a catchment to precipitation, reflects the integrated effects of a wide range of land cover, soil, topography, climate and precipitation characteristics of the area. There are many ways to figure out runoff and to her hydrological elements. Hydrological modelling is one efficient way for rational long term behavioral studies. Hydrological modelling is a mathematical representation of natural processes that influence primarily the energy and water balances of a particular watershed. SWAT model (Soil and Water Assessment Tool), MIKE SHE model (Systeme Hydrologique European), HBV model (Hydrologiska Byrans Vattenavdelning model), TOPMODEL, Variable infiltration Capacity (VIC) model, HEC-HMS (Hydrologic Engineering Centre Hydrologic Modelling System) are some of the physically based distributed hydrologic models. Large data is managed by Geographic Information systems (GIS) and have captured attention of various analyst. GIS is equipped with huge storage and pre-processing capabilities for the data needed in analysis, and it assist to map the results. GIS thus facilitate to compile spatial geomorphic and hydrological data of the basin used for parameters estimation.

Keywords: Runoff, hydrological mode, VIC, GIS

I. INTRODUCTION

Water resources management needs a proper way to handle a particular approach. It involves various hydrological components. There is impact on various environmental parameter like land use and land cover, agriculture, water usage due to human encroachment on environment at significant level. The impact leads to periodic hydrologic change. It thus becomes necessary to understand and quantify various hydrological components of the catchment for efficient management of water. Runoff representing the response of a catchment to precipitation, reflects the integrated effects of a wide range of land cover, soil, topography, climate and precipitation characteristics of the area. There are many ways to figure out runoff and to her hydrological elements. Throughout the world many attempts are made to build a model and forecast rainfall as rainfall is primary component of hydrological cycle. Runoff is excess water that flows on surface of ground. It occurs when rate of precipitation exceeds rate of percolation of water in ground. Precipitation is major element in hydrological cycle... For implementation of water management, accurate prediction of runoff is very important. Rainfall runoff models are hydrological models that stimulate rainfall runoff relation. Runoff is cumulative effect of land use land cover, environment, modification in agricultural method, new water related projects,

change in precipitation. Human modification in environment had significantly caused seasonal and yearly hydrologic variations. In recent times this variation had a great impact on river basin. These basins has to face an extreme conditions of drought, flood, cyclones etc. This indicates that there is shift in hydrological behavior of catchment. The alteration of rainfall pattern can be correlated with various water related hurdles like drought, flooding, water logging, etc. It thus becomes necessary to identify and quantify various hydrological components of the catchment for efficient water resource management. Efforts are been made to describe hydrological phenomenon in physical terms from pixel to catchment scale. In computation of model uncertainty is often neglected. The main reason is lack of input data. Thus for accurate computation of hydrological model input data has to be accumulated properly. Large data is managed by Geographic Information systems (GIS) and have captured attention of various analyst. GIS is equipped with huge storage and pre-processing capabilities for the data needed in analysis, and it assist to map the results. GIS thus facilitate to compile spatial geomorphic and hydrological data of the basin used for parameters estimation. Hydrological modelling is a mathematical representation of natural processes that influence primarily the energy and water balances of a particular watershed. SWAT model (Soil and Water Assessment Tool), MIKE SHE model (Système Hydrologique European), HBV model (Hydrologiska Byrans Vattenavdelning model), TOPMODEL, Variable infiltration Capacity (VIC) model, HEC-HMS (Hydrologic Engineering Centre Hydrologic Modelling System) are some of the physically based distributed hydrologic models.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the year many analyst have highlighted on past water resource and have predicted future resources. (Liang et al., 1994; Alcamo et al., 1997; Hagemann and Gates, 2001; Takata et al., 2003; Krinner et al., 2005; Bondeau et al., 2007; Hanasaki et al., 2008; Van Beek and Bierkens, 2008; Best et al., 2011). Rainfall is crucial component of the hydrological cycle, which is of great significance. It is utilized in various scientific areas like meteorology, hydrology, etc (Bin Zhu 2020). Various efforts are made to measure the hydrologic behavior of the river basin, due to different land covers (Shaini Naha, 2021). The future prediction of Hydrologic models predict the spatial and temporal distribution of water and energy at the land surface. It is observed that the present available parameter are shortfall to global-scale hydrologic modelling to very coarse resolution, hindering researchers from resolving fine-scale variability. (Jacob R. Schaperow, 2021) The complex topography, season variation of river basin that further complicate calibration of model parameter, are major for hydrological modelling. Time variant sensitivity in model (Ajay Bajracharya, 2020) there is fluctuation in the magnitude of surface runoff, aquifer recharge, and river flows due to Land use/land cover (LULC) and climate change. The evaluation helps to identify the level of water resources exposure to the changes that could help to plan for potential adaptive capacity (Wakjira Takala Dibaba, 2020) the basin wise water resources potential for the India was assessed based on empirical approaches long back. However, over a period of time, climate has significantly changed; and simultaneous due to the developmental activities going on in the country, land use land cover (LULC) pattern in each river basins has been modified. (Vaibhav Garg 2019). Using environmental models

correctly involves much more than knowledge about the required inputs and resulting outputs. It is important to follow good modelling practices and to have realistic expectations about what can be achieved (Carolina Massmann 2014) the inability to conduct hydrological simulations in areas that lack historical meteorological data is an important factor limiting the development of watershed models, understanding of watershed water resources, and ultimate development of effective sustainability policies. (Xinchen Gu 2020). Hydrological responses corresponding to the agricultural land use alterations are critical for planning crop management strategies, water resources management, and environmental evaluations. However, accurate estimation and evaluation of these hydrological responses are restricted by the limited availability of detailed crop classification in land use and land cover. (Ankur Srivastava 2020).

Hydrological models are used for various purposes, including flow forecasting, flood forecasting and short and long term water management. However, models suffer from uncertainties from different sources, such as parameterisation, input data errors and process descriptions. To obtain reliable information for planning and management, hydrologic models are needed to simulate the rainfall-runoff relationship (Pradhan and Indu 2019 Even though the actual processes are more complex than their model representations, predictive capabilities can be improved through calibration to find optimal model parameters for the best fit between simulated and observed characteristics (Guo et al. 2014; Yen et al. 2014). The choice of a hydrological model depends on the purpose of its utilisation and data availability The continuous improvement of computer skills and the development of science and technology has concurrently led to the rapid development of digital elevation model (DEM), geographic information system (GIS) and remote sensing (RS) technology(Abbott, M.B.1996).The Variable Infiltration Capacity (VIC) model (Liang et al.1994) is a semi-distributed macroscale hydrologic model(MHM) that has been applied in a broad set of use cases. The model has been used for numerous water and energy balance studies in the US (Abdulla and Lettenmaier, 1997; Nijssen et al., 1997), the Arctic (Adam and Lettenmaier, 2008; Suet al., 2005; Tan et al., 2011; Hamman et al., 2016), and globally (Nijssen et al., 2001a, b, c; Sheffield et al., 2009). Hydrological modelling tools have been increasingly used worldwide in the management of water resources at watershed level. Understanding the hydrologic response of very large river basins offers new challenges and opportunities for hydrologists. Traditionally, hydrologists have tended to focus on catchments or watersheds ranging from plot scale research sites (typically 0.1–2 km²), to small experimental catchments (0.1–10 km²), and occasionally medium sized catchments (10²–10³ km²). (Dennis P. LETTENMAIER 2001). The application of these tools has recently improved with the advent of remote sensing and geographic information system (GIS) techniques RUI HE & BO PANG 2015) Since it was developed, the VIC model has been widely used in runoff simulation research, the effects of climate change on water resources, land-atmosphere coupling, and national daily soil moisture simulations; in addition, it has been successfully applied at different watershed scales. The Variable Infiltration Capacity (VIC) model is a semi-distributed macroscale hydrological model. Development of the VIC began in the early 1990s, and the model has since been widely used for applications ranging from basin to global applications, which include the construction of hydrologic datasets, analysis of hydrologic flow trends and states, data evaluation and assimilation,

forecasting, coupled climate modelling, and climate. Assessment of the impact of the change. Ongoing operational applications of the VIC model include the University of Washington Drought Monitoring and Forecasting Systems and the NASA Soil Data Assimilation System. (Joseph J. Hamman 2018) In all cases, studying model sensitivity and parameter uncertainty is paramount to avoid biased results. In prediction analysis (e.g. Surfleet et al. 2012; Yen et al. 2014). Most hydrological models include many parameters to characterize hydrological processes. These are measured or estimated from catchment characteristics (e.g., Montanari et al. 2013; Sood and Smakhtin 2015; Guse et al. 2019; Patnaik et al. 2019) VIC generates surface runoff and base flow, taking into account vegetation heterogeneity in each grid cell, different soil layers with variable infiltration, land topography to capture precipitation and temperature changes in relation to land elevation, coupled fluxes of water and energy between land surface and atmosphere, snow accumulation, melting and ablation, and nonlinear base flow. In addition, the flow routing of the VIC model (RVIC) (Lohmann et al. 1996, 1998) is used to route runoff and base flow generated by the VIC to the catchment outlet based on a unit hydrographic convolution equation coupled with linearized Saint-Venant equations. The VIC (VIC-5) model was released (Hamman et al. al., 2018), which focused on improving the model infrastructure. These improvements are highly relevant in simulating anthropogenic impacts on global water resources. Ongoing model application Real-time VICs include the University of California, Los Angeles Drought Monitoring and Forecasting Systems ([http://www.hydro.ucla.edu/Surface Water Group/forecast/monitor/index.shtml](http://www.hydro.ucla.edu/Surface%20Water%20Group/forecast/monitor/index.shtml), last accessed: 20 August 2018) and NASA Land Data Assimilation System (LDAS; <https://ldas.gsfc.nasa.gov>, last accessed: 20 August 2018)

3. LARGESCALE HYDROLOGICAL MODELING

The fundamental purpose of modelling the hydrology is to gain an overall understanding of the complex hydrological system and its dynamics in order to provide reliable information to water resource managers and policy makers (Bhattacharya et al., 2013). A large-scale hydrological modelling encompasses water resources development and management at river basin scale. Such models operate on large area, across regional and administrative boundaries, and includes different geophysical and climatic zones. The specific objective behind development of large area hydrological model is to produce a tool that can be used in large catchments for a variety of applications, including: a) Flood forecasting b) Assessing the effects of river regulation measures c) Assessing the effects of land-use change d) Assessing the effects of climate change e) Management of water supplies in arid regions. With advent of computer in terms of hardware, software, increased speed and storage, debugging tools and availability of advanced GIS software's have made large area simulation possible. The challenging task is then developing a basin-scale model that: (1) is computationally efficient; (2) allows considerable spatial detail; (3) requires readily available inputs; (4) is continuous-time; (5) is capable of simulating land-management scenarios; and (6) gives reasonable results. The model must correctly reflect changes in land use and agricultural management on stream flow and sediment yield. Available models with these capabilities are usually limited by spatial scale. Available river basin models generally do not adequately link results to land use and management to assess management

strategies. VIC family model (Wood et al., 1992; Liang et al., 1994), ISBA-MODCOU (Habets et al., 1999), LARS 1M (Bremicker, 1998) and WATFLOOD (Soulis et al., 2004)

3.1. Historical Background

The variable invasion volume (VIC) model (Liang et al., 1994, 1996) has undergone several modifications (Cherkauer et al., 2003; Bowling et al., 2004; Bowling and Lettenmaier, 2009). The VIC model is characterized by a nonlinear reduction in drainage from zones of low soil moisture. There are also subcluster variations in soil water storage capacity and surface vegetation. Topographic rainfall and temperature drop rates provide more realistic hydrology. Semi distributed macroscale models are used in numerous studies based on water resources, climate change, and land-atmosphere interactions. VIC can balance the water and surface energy balance. When combined with a general circulation model, it also plays an important role as a hydrological model as a land surface scheme. The VIC model is widely used in large river basins around the world due to its various properties. Globus (Abdulla et al. 1996; Bowling et al. 2000; Lohmann et al. 1998b; Nijssen et al. 1997, 2001a, 2008; Su et al., 2005, 2006. Holtz et al. 1997; Zhu and Lettenmaier, 2007). The VIC model was observed to perform well compared to available observations and other schemes (Bowling et al., 2003a, b; Lohmann et al., 2004; Nijssen et al. 2003; Wood et al., 1998). Participation in the WCRP Inter comparison of Land Surface Parameterization Schemes (PILPS) project and the North American Land Data Assimilation System (NLDAS). Its performance has been observed using US soil moisture observations (Maurer et al., 2002) and global snow cover data (Nijssen et al., 2001b).

3.2. Overview of the Vic Model

The VIC model was designed to be integrated into the GCM with the aim of improving the horizontal fit representation and subgrid non-uniformity in a simpler way. VIC was first described by Wood et al. using the water permeation system of the Xianjiang model (Zhao, 1980). Described as a single layer model. (1992), submitted to the GCM GFDL and the Max Planck Institute (MPI) (Stamm et al. 1994). A single soil layer model requires three parameters: a seepage parameter, an evaporation parameter, and a base flow regression coefficient. In 1994, Liang et al. (1994) generally developed a two-layer VIC model (VIC-2L) to integrate multiple layers of soil and vegetation and evaporation within grid cells. VIC-2L calculates inflow, topsoil-to-subsoil water flow, and surface and groundwater flow over each plant cover plate (statistical parameters for infiltration and flow heterogeneity within existing plant cover plates). In addition to the conversion. Original VIC model). Therefore, subcluster heterogeneity is represented by soil moisture retention, evaporation and flow generation. A slightly distributed model of the Earth, the VIC, which calculates apparent and subtle temperature changes as a function of body composition, uses conceptual schemes to represent water flow and baseline flow. To do. In 1996, Liang et al. (1996) VIC-2L found that low soil moisture in the topsoil tends to dampen evaporation. The main reason for this failure is the lack of a soil-to-topsoil moisture transfer mechanism. We then modified the VIC-2L to allow moisture to diffuse between the soil layers, forming a thin soil layer more than 10 cm above the previous surface layer. This is how the three-layer VIC model (VIC-3L) was developed, and the VIC-3L

framework has been used ever since. The model now allows more than two soil layers if desired. Vic Modification values were developed to improve the model to deal with complex hydrological processes. VIC model is below another route model was developed to mimic river flow, as it does not represent the geometry of the grid dispersion (Lohmann., et al., 1996, 1998a, 1998b). To represent the global warming process, the VIC model was developed and includes a dual intensity ice model (Andreadis et al., 2009; Wigmosta et al., 1994; Storck et al., 1998), frozen soil and permafrost algorithms (Cherkauer et al., 1999, 2003; Cherkauer and Lettenmaier, 2003) and Hurricane Ice Algorithm (Bowling et al., 2004). In order to improve the simulation of height-dependent components within a grid cell, terrain height bands were introduced (Nijssen et al., 2001b). The evapotranspiration algorithm incorporates canopy response to atmospheric profile and radiation balance (Wigmosta et al., 1994), leaf area index (LAI) and plant parts may vary between stages (Liang et al., 1996). The impact of ponds and wetlands on water retention and evaporation, which is essential for large water flows, has been considered (Bowling et al., 2003c; Bowling and Lettenmaier, 2009; Cherkauer et al., 2003). A management effects, reservoir module was applied to the root model and a spray irrigation scheme was added to the soil moisture model (Haddeland et al., 2006a, 2006b, 2007).

4. MODEL INPUTS

The VIC model requires several sets of input data and are broadly categorized into:

- 1. Meteorological Forcing Files:** VIC can take daily or sub-daily time-series of meteorological variables as inputs for each grid separately
- 2. Soil Parameter File:** The soil parameter predominantly defines the grid-wise, layer-wise soil hydraulic particulars and along with model control parameters. The soil hydraulic parameters include saturated hydraulic conductivity, density, maximum soil moisture holding capacity, etc.
- 3. Vegetation Parameter & Library File:** Land cover types, fractional areas, rooting depths, and seasonal LAIs of the various land cover tiles within each grid cell.
- 4. Global Parameter File:** This is the main input file for VIC. It points VIC to the locations of the other input/output files and sets parameters that govern the simulation and model run
- 5. Routing Parameter File:** Grid-wise elevation, direction of flow, slope, catchment fraction, diffusion

5. CHARACTERISTICS OF BASINS

Elements relating to twenty river valleys are presented in the following sections.

5.1 Indus (within India)

The Indus region extends to the provinces of Jammu and Kashmir (60.31%), Himachal Pradesh (15.98%), Punjab (15.66%), and part of Rajasthan (4.92%), Haryana (3.09%), with the exception of the Union Territory of Chandigarh (0.04%). %) with an area of 3,17,708 sq.km which is approximately 9.8 percent of the total area (Figure 3.14). The depth of the pit area is

between 72 ° 28 ' to 79 ° 39 ' Eastern East and 29 ° 8 ' ' to 36 ° 59 ' in the northern parts of the country. The upper part of the basin, located in Jammu and Kashmir and Himachal Pradesh, is dominated by mountains and small valleys. In Punjab, Haryana and Rajasthan, the basin consists of vast plateaus, the fertile desert of the country.

Fig 1: Percentage of Indus area in various provinces

There are 6 major rivers flowing in this valley namely, Indus, Jhelum, Chenab, Ravi, Beas and Sutlej. The southwest monsoon brings rain during the summer months while winter rains are caused by storms in Jammu and Kashmir. The average annual rainfall during the study period is 896 mm in the container. During the study period (1985 to 2015) the maximum rainfall was recorded at 1315.6 mm in 1995-96 and at least 512.6 mm in 2000-01. Temperature. The Indus basin is responsible for varying the temperature from the upper part of the vessel to the lower part of the container. The difference may be due to differences in the topography of the container. Temperatures are below 0oC in the upper part of the Indus basin, while temperatures rise above 40oC in the lower part of the basin.

5.2 Ganga-Brahmaputra-Meghna

5.2.1 Ganga

The Ganga basin outspreads in India, Tibet (China), Nepal and Bangladesh over an area of 10,86,000 sq.km. In India, it covers states of Uttar Pradesh (28.68%), Madhya Pradesh (21.65%), Rajasthan (11.22%), Bihar(12.86%), West Bengal (8.37%), Uttarakh and (6.38%), Jharkhand (6.04%), Haryana (1.59%), Chhattisgarh (2.20%), Himachal Pradesh (0.71%) and Union Territory of Delhi (0.18%) draining an area of 8,38,803 sq.km which is nearly 26% of the total geographical area of the country (Figure No 3.15). The basin lies between East longitudes 73°2' to 89°5' and North latitudes 21°6' to 31°21' having maximum length and width of approximately 1,543 km and 1,024 km. The basin is bounded by the Himalayas on the north, the Aravalli on the west, the Vindhya and Chhotanagpur plateau on the south and the Brahmaputra Ridge on the east. Mean annual rainfall of the study time period is 1,007 mm for the basin.

Fig 2: Percentage area of Ganga basin in various States

5.2.2 Brahmaputra

The Brahmaputra basin spreads over countries of Tibet (China), Bhutan, India and Bangladesh having a total area of 5, 80,000 sq.km. In India, it spreads over states of Arunachal Pradesh (42.60%), Assam (36.46%), West Bengal (5.92%), Meghalaya (5.70%), Nagaland (5.63%) and Sikkim (3.69%) and lies between 88°11' to 96°57' East longitudes and 24°44' to 30°3' North latitudes and extends over an area of 1,93,252 sq.km which is nearly 5.9% of the total geographical area of the country (Figure 3.16). It is bounded by the Himalayas on the north, the Patkari range of hills on the east running along the India-Myanmar border, the Assam range of hills on the south and the Himalayas and the ridge separating it from Ganga basin on the west. The Brahmaputra River originates in the north from Kailash ranges of Himalayas at an elevation of 5,150 m just south of the lake called Konggyu Tsho and flows for about a total length of 2,900 km. In India, it flows for 916 km. The major part of basin is covered with forest accounting to 55.48% of the total area and 5.79% of the basin is covered by water bodies. Mean annual rainfall of the study time period is 2,330 mm (IMD rainfall) for the basin. Reassessment of water availability in basins using space inputs.

Fig 3: Percentage area of Brahmaputra basin in various States

5.2.3 Barak & others

The Barak & others basin extends over an area of 86,335 sq.km, which is nearly 1.44% of the total geographical area of the country. The basin covers the states of Meghalaya (24%), Manipur (20%), Mizoram (19%), Tripura (18%), Assam (17%) and Nagaland (2%) (Figure

3.17). The Barak River rises from the Manipur Hills, south of Mao in Senapati District at an elevation of 2,331 m. Then it flows along Nagaland-Manipur border through hilly terrains and enters Assam. It further enters Bangladesh where it is known by the Surma and the Kushiya and later called the Meghna before receiving combined flow of the Ganga and the Brahmaputra. Annual rainfall of the basin varies from 1,975 mm to 3,518 mm. The average annual rainfall (1985-2015) in the Barak & others basin is 2,625 mm. Climate: The Barak & other basins has a tropical climate. The average annual monthly maximum temperature is about 27.9°C and average annual minimum temperature is about 26.5°C in the basin. Temperatures in the bordering region with Bangladesh are higher, whereas in interior location temperature is moderate.

Fig 4: Percentage area of Barak & others basin in various States

5.3 Godavari

The Godavari basin extends over an area of 3, 12,150 sq.km, which is nearly 9.5% of the total geographical area of the country. The basin lies in the states of Maharashtra (48.50%), Andhra Pradesh & Telangana (23.30%), Chhattisgarh (12.50%), Madhya Pradesh (8.6%), Odisha (5.70%), and Karnataka (1.40%). Godavari is a perennial and the second largest river draining in India. Godavari River originates near Trayambakeswar near Nasik, northeast of Mumbai in the state of Maharashtra at an elevation of 1,067 m and flows for a length of about 1,465 km before joining the Bay of Bengal. It flows through the Eastern Ghats and emerges out at Polavaram into the plains. Annual rainfall of the basin varies from 877 mm to 1,493 mm. The mean annual rainfall (1985-2015) in the Godavari basin is 1,117 mm. Climate: The Godavari basin has a tropical climate. The temperature varies from 20oC to 35oC in a year which causes lot of monthly variations in the potential evapotranspiration in the Reassessment of water availability in basins using space inputs basin. Minimum potential evapotranspiration in the basin is 30 to 100 mm during January/February and maximum goes up to 400 mm to 450 mm during April/May months.

Fig 5: Percentage area of Godavari basin in various States

5.4 Krishna

The Krishna basin extends over an area of 2, 59,439 sq.km, which is nearly 7.9% of the total geographical area of the country. Krishna basin lies in the states of Maharashtra (26.60%), Karnataka (43.80%), Telangana (19.80%) and Andhra Pradesh (9.80%) (Figure 3.19). The river Krishna is a perennial river and second largest eastward draining interstate river in Peninsular India. The river rises from the Western Ghats near Jor village of Satara district of Maharashtra at an altitude of 1,337 m just north of Mahabaleshwar. The total length of river from origin to its outfall into the Bay of Bengal is 1400 km. months. The other rainy seasons are not so well defined and well spread as the South-West monsoon season.

Rainfall: Rainfall varies both spatially and temporally in Krishna basin. Annual rainfall of the basin varies from 604 mm to 1,045 mm and the mean annual rainfall (1985-2015) in the Krishna basin is 841 mm. Many times basin receives high rainfall in less duration causing floods in those years. **Climate:** The Krishna basin has a tropical climate. The mean monthly maximum and minimum temperature is about 32.1°C and 26.5°C in the basin respectively. Temperatures in the coastal region are moderate but humidity is higher.

Fig 6: Percentage area of Krishna basin in various States

Conclusion

A rapid progress is made from the rational method to distributed hydrological models in catchment hydrology. Several decades of research resulted in vast evolution of conceptualization and parameterization of hydrological processes. Proponents of physically based models have put enormous efforts to describe hydrological phenomenon in physical terms from pixel to catchment scale. Analysis of uncertainty is often neglected by the hydrologist in evaluation of complex computational models. In general, however, there has been very little work reported on the shape of parameter distributions and the effect on prediction uncertainty. The review indicated that VIC model is capable of simulating hydrological processes with reasonable accuracy and can be applied to large ungauged basin.

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